

THE REPRESENTATION AND FUNCTION OF NATURE IN "THE MINISTRY FOR THE FUTURE" BY KIM STANLEY ROBINSON

Yusupova Sabina G'ulomjon qizi

Masters student

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

syusupova145@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19088516>

Abstract

The article aims to analyze the representation and role of nature in the novel "The Ministry for the Future" by Kim Stanley Robinson, written from the point of view of ecocriticism. It is argued that nature is an active agent that organizes ethics, politics, and international responses to climate crises, emphasizing human nature interconnectedness and developing ecological consciousness and accountability in addressing global challenges within contemporary society.

Keywords: ecocriticism, climate fiction, environmental imagination, ecological crisis, ecological ethics

Introduction

The representation and role of nature are the central concerns of ecocriticism, which as an area of study focuses on the interconnectedness between literature and the physical environment. "The Ministry for the Future" is a climate-fiction novel which is written by American novelist Kim Stanley Robinson, is the best known for his Mars trilogy, examines a near future world confronting with increasing global ecological catastrophe [Robinson, 2020:3]. It describes the worldwide collapse around nations and societies, showing how countries deal with global warming and ecological degradation, progressive destabilization of natural systems. In the novel, the nature is not non-active setting, but it is explored as a dynamically unstable force which contracts human pressures and insists on emerging ethical and political strategies. Robinson represents landscapes, oceans, changing climate patterns, and all creatures evolving more rapidly than humans can adapt. The author allows environmental mechanisms engaging in real figures, as a result the distinction between ecological transformation and direction intervention is diminished. By doing this, nature is expressed as both a victim which is affected by mankind's actions and a significant force that determining the future of humanity.

In "The Ministry for the Future", Robinson chooses to show the nature with all its multifaceted and interlinked appearances such as in climate, landscapes, animal life, and ecosystems in order to emphasize the dynamic and active role of the planet itself [Garrard, 2004:11]. In the first sequence of the novel, the devastating heatwave occurring in India, the active role of nature is noted, where thousands of people die due to temperatures reaching beyond the livable limits [Robinson, 2020:25]. This highlights how nature is not merely a passive presence but also has the power to render moral value. This is supported by Buell when it is noted, "Nature-writing attributes an active presence to the more-than-human world, which exerts a shaping influence on human beings and their ethics". The performative role of nature persists throughout the narrative, interacting and influencing individual and global responses [Clark, 2011:34]. Climate-related disasters, rising sea levels, and melting glaciers act

as natural forces of accountability, which impose punishments for human abuse. In this regard, Robinson is consonant with Buell, who argues that eco-literature has the role of instilling ethical senses by dramatizing the human body's relation to nature. What happens in Nature propels the narrative, shapes political alignments, sparks scientific discoveries, and induces philosophical awareness[Buell,2001:84].

In aesthetic and artistic expression, Robinson establishes his planetary story by incorporating elements of nature. His work, which has a polyphonic structure consisting of voices including but not limited to scientists, refugees, and economists, and further including voices of other than human beings, portrays the interconnections between ecological systems[Heise,2008:101]. In his book, the concept of Garrard regarding nature as a discursive construct is represented by the numerous interpretations associated with various cultures, politics, and languages. Symbolically, ice also manifests itself as one of the most important natural elements in the novel. The meltdown of polar ice caps serves not only as a planetary hazard but also has strong symbolic meaning when it points to the sensitivity of the planet's structure and ethics. The planetary endeavor to refreeze the ice caps by geo-engineering is significantly indicative of human ingenuity to recreate balance, which aptly encompasses the ecocentric notion of Glotfelty to connect literature and ethics. The presence of the animal and the non-human in the novel, though often voiceless, serves to develop the theme of interdependence. What is interesting feature is the occasional voice, often more metaphorical than anything, which the author gives to ecosystems and species as if to convey that the natural world, too, is valuable and conscious. This is very much on the right path when it comes to following the suggestion offered by Glotfelty regarding an ecocentric approach to literature and the corresponding attention to narratives reflecting more of an overarching, global perspective than a human-centered one.

In philosophical terms, the concept of nature depicted by Robinson is very much aligned to Buell's concept of environmental imagination, which argues that literature has the power to influence ecological consciousness by transforming the notion of human and nonhuman. In turn, Garrard's description of the tropes of environment, such as apocalypse, wilderness, and dwelling, finds expression in Robinson's world, which moves between hope and hopelessness, chaos and integrity, reflecting the tension found in ecological discourse. At the same time, the importance of ecocriticism, which is defined by Glotfelty, highlights the ethics of literature, which needs to respond to the global realities of ecological crises and provoke a universal ethical reaction. Ultimately, the story told by Robinson is clearly ecocentric, showing humans to be part of a large, self-balancing system rather than the rulers of it.

Conclusion

Taking everything into account, in the novel "The Ministry for the Future", nature plays a pivotal role in shaping the narrative and conveying a core message of the book. The author represents the elements of nature as unpredictable and often overwhelming, which stimulates readers to overthink about the interaction between human beings and the environment they are living in, addressing them to the urgency of Earth's preservation[Buell,2001:112]. The aesthetic and performative roles of nature are juxtaposed, indicating environmental upheaval while examining the book's intellectual and moral questions[Clark,2011:89]. The novel allows readers to transform institutions, reform economic concerns and organize new forms of international cooperation by readers now consider how human life and planet is

interconnected each other. In the end, Robinson illustrates the nature not as a passive context but as an active manifestation.

References:

1. Buell, L. (1995). *The Environmental Imagination: Thoreau, Nature Writing, and the Formation of American Culture*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1995. – 385p.
2. Buell, L. (2001). *Writing for an Endangered World: Literature, Culture, and Environment in the United States and Beyond*. Cambridge: Cambridge university press, 2001. - 240 p.
3. Clark, T. (2011). *The Cambridge Introduction to Literature and the Environment*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press, 2011. –276 p.
4. Garrard, G. (2004). *Ecocriticism*. 2nd ed. Routledge, 2012. – 272 p.
5. Glotfelty, C., & Fromm, H. (Eds.). (1996). *The Ecocriticism Reader: Landmarks in Literary Ecology*. Athens, GA: University of Georgia Press, 1996 – 415p.
6. Heise, U. K. (2008). *Sense of Place and Sense of Planet: The Environmental Imagination of the Global*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008. – 264 p.
7. Robinson, K.S. *The Ministry for the Future*. –New York: Orb, 2020. – 576 p.